

Mannich Bases from 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl- and 7-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethyl-coumarins as Possible Central Nervous System Stimulants

Satyendra Kumar and Shiam Sunder Joshi

The previous work¹⁻³ has been further extended to the synthesis of some Mannich bases from 4-methyl-6-ethyl- and 4,6-dimethyl-umbelliferones. These coumarins have been prepared from ethylacetoacetate and 4-ethyl- and 4-methyl-resorcinol respectively, using polyphosphoric acid as the condensing agent. The latter has been found to be superior to sulphuric acid, used earlier for this purpose.

The coumarins, when refluxed with paraformaldehyde and different secondary amines, namely, dimethylamine, diethylamine, di-isobutylamine, di-isoamylamine, di-ethanolamine, dibenzylamine, piperidine, morpholine, pyrrolidine, and *N*-methylpiperazine, in anhydrous ethanol, yield the corresponding Mannich bases. These have been isolated as hydrochlorides and are described in Tables I and II.

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin.—A mixture of 4-ethylresorcinol (13.8 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (13 g.), and polyphosphoric acid (200 g.) was heated on a steam bath for half an hour and then poured on crushed ice. The solid (18 g.) separating was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 213°. (Found: C, 70.53; H, 5.80. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₂O₃: C, 70.58; H, 5.88%).

7-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethylcoumarin (16.5 g.) was prepared by the method described above, using 4-methylresorcinol (12.4 g.). It was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 254° (decomp.). (Found: C, 69.41; H, 5.14. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₃: C, 69.47; H, 5.26%).

Mannich base hydrochlorides from these coumarins were prepared by the procedure described earlier².

One of the authors (S.K.) is thankful to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India, for the award of a research scholarship.

1. Kumar and Joshi, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 149.

2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 200.

3. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 473.

TABLE II

N-Substituted 7-hydroxy-4,6-dimethyl-8-aminomethylcoumarin hydrochlorides.

No.	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.		% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ NCl	188-90°	36%	59.17	59.85	6.41	6.34	4.85	4.93	12.49	12.52
2	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ NCl	138°	45	61.50	61.63	7.17	7.06	4.52	4.49	11.31	11.39
3	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ O ₃ NCl	275°(d)	40	65.35	65.30	8.10	8.16	3.72	3.80	0.72	0.65
4	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ O ₃ NCl	295°(d)	25	68.70	66.75	8.49	8.59	3.60	3.53	8.83	8.97
5	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ NCl	249°	60	55.98	55.89	6.31	6.40	4.14	4.07	10.40	10.33
6	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₃ NCl	245°	55	71.73	71.64	5.89	5.97	3.30	3.21	8.22	8.15
7	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ NCl	300°	50	63.14	63.06	6.72	6.80	4.40	4.52	10.86	10.97
8	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ NCl	202°	52	58.91	58.08	6.08	6.14	4.25	4.30	10.98	10.80
9	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ NCl	300°	48	62.17	62.03	6.40	6.46	4.43	4.52	11.55	11.46
10	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	240°	28	60.28	60.26	6.71	6.79	8.34	8.26	10.55	10.48

* The substituents (R) are in the same serial order as in Table I. (d) — denotes decomposition.

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MERRY COLLEGE,
MERRY, N. H.

Received June 13, 1964.

PRESIDENT :

S. H. ZAHED, M.A., Ph.D.

VICE-PRESIDENTS :

(who have filled the office of President)

P. K. BOSE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

N. R. DEB, D.Sc., DEES. SO., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

J. N. MUKHERJEE, C.B.E., D.Sc.,

F.A.S.B., F.N.I.

MATA PRASAD, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

J. N. RAY, O.B.E., D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

P. RAY, M.A., F.N.I.

T. R. SESHADRI, M.A., Ph.D., F.R.S.

R. C. SHAH, B.A., M.Sc., Ph.D., F.N.I., F.R.I.C.

K. VENKATARAMAN, D.Sc., F.N.I.

VICE-PRESIDENTS :

K. S. G. DOSS, D.Sc., F.N.I., F.R.I.C.,

F.INST.P.

B. N. GHOSH, D.Sc., F.N.I.

R. H. SAHASRABUDHEY, M.Sc., Ph.D., D.Sc.,
F.R.I.C.,

President of Banaras Branch (*ex-officio*)

HONY. SECRETARY :

M. M. CHAKRABARTY, M.Sc., Ph.D., F.R.I.C.

HONY. TREASURER :

D. CHAKRABARTI, D.Sc., F.N.I.

MEMBERS OF THE COUNCIL :

V. BALLAH, M.Sc., Ph.D.

D. K. BANERJEE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

S. K. BHATTACHARYA, D.Sc., F.N.I.

(Mrs.) A. CHATTERJEE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

B. CHATTERJEE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

A. K. DEY, M.Sc., D.Phil., D.Sc., F.N.A.Sc.,

SATYESWAR GHOSH, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

B. C. HALDAR, D.Sc.

B. H. IYER, M.Sc., Ph.D., A.L.I.Sc., F.R.I.C.,

A. B. KULKARNI, D.Sc.,

R. P. MITRA, D.Sc., F.N.I.

S. K. MUKHERJEE, D.Sc.

S. R. PALIT, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

M. K. ROUT, D.Sc., Ph.D.

S. M. SETHNA, M.Sc., Ph.D.

J. SHANKAR, M.Sc., Ph.D., F.N.I.

R. D. TEWARI, M.Sc., Ph.D., F.N.I.

REV. L. M. YEDDANAPALLI, M.A., Ph.D., D.Sc.,
F.R.I.C.

HONY. EDITORS :

S. M. MUKHERJI, D.Sc., F.N.I.

R. C. MEBOTRA D.Phil., Ph.D., F.R.I.C.

BOARD OF ASSOCIATE EDITORS :

D. K. BANERJEE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

U. P. BASU, D.Sc., F.N.I.

B. CHATTERJEE, D.Sc., F.N.I.

R. D. DEB, D.Sc., F.N.I.,

B. N. GHOSH, D.Sc., F.N.I.

S. N. MUKHERJEE, D.Sc.

S. K. MUKHERJEE, D.Sc.

S. R. PALIT, D.Sc., F.R.I.C., F.N.I.

B. PRASAD, D.Sc., F.N.I.

P. RAY, M.A., F.N.I.

D. K. ROY, D.Sc.

S. M. SETHNA, M.Sc., Ph.D.

HONY. AUDITORS :

P. C. NANDI, M.A., B.Sc., A.C.A.R.A.

A. B. GUPTA, B.Sc., LL.B., A.C.A.R.A.

ASST. EDITOR :

G. BANERJEE, M.Sc